

Piloting Status of the Location-enabled LEDSOL Solution for Access to Clean Water in Africa

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Abstract This is a work-in-progress paper presenting the current status of the transnational LEDSOL (“Enabling clean and sustainable water through smart UV/LED disinfection and SOLar energy utilization”) project and system, which integrates an UV/LED-based water disinfection unit with a positioning engine for location-enabled features and with a solar-cell-based power source. The prototype has already been tested with water from three lakes in Romania and the piloting has just started in Algeria and Togo and will have a static-testing phase and a dynamic-testing phase. The water purification unit comprises a particle filter, an active carbon filter and a disinfection unit consisting of three UV/LED tubes. The disinfection unit has already shown very good water purification capability. In terms of location engines, two apps have been used to collect data from Android mass-market devices: the GNSSLogger app provided by Google and a MIMIR app developed by Tampere University team; only the former one has been so far used to collect data from Africa. In addition, a GNSS constellation simulator has been developed in Matlab in order to be able to model various GNSS-related parameters. These features are to be further integrated as Location-Based Service (LBS) into the LEDSOL portable water disinfection system for real-time monitoring and alerts, optimized routing and

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deployment of the water portable units, as well as collecting and analyzing data on water quality and usage patterns across different locations. This paper also shows some snapshot results obtained with our simulator and three tracks collected from three locations in Africa, in Togo, Algeria, and Tanzania. The further integration efforts and the next steps in LEDSOL project are also discussed.

1 Location-enabled solutions for better access to clean water

The ongoing international LEDSOL¹ project aims to provide real-time clean water solutions using a smart portable unit that combines UV/LED disinfection with classical decontamination, powered by renewable energy sources and equipped with a mobile tracking unit, based, for example of Galileo Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) signals collected from affordable end-user devices. The development of a LBS app for multi-purpose data collection and analysis and real-time monitoring of the portable disinfection units will span beyond the LEDSOL's project end.

In our LEDSOL publications so far, we have already highlighted the value of inexpensive, universal wireless positioning solutions for enhanced water management in Africa [1, 2]. While the positioning engine is not critical for an adequate functioning of the system towards the water disinfection and purification, it can add value to the overall mobile solution as follows:

1. Providing a location-based optimization of resources, e.g., by ensuring that disinfection units are deployed where they are most needed;
2. Monitoring and tracking, e.g., by keeping track of the locations and movements of disinfection units for better management.
3. Location-based data collection and analytics, by gathering location-based data to analyze and to improve water disinfection strategies according to location-tagged outputs;
4. Improving accessibility by ensuring that remote or under-served areas receive adequate water disinfection services.

The current literature on improving the access to clean water in Africa is scarce, as pointed for example in a recent scoping review from November 2024 [3]. The market potential of location-based services (LBS) in the context of water management has also been scarcely addressed so far in the existing literature; an example which discusses the market potential of LBS for different utilities including water, can be found in [4].

The first stages of the LEDSOL project have been completed and a prototype has already been delivered for further pilot tests in Algeria and Togo. This work in progress paper describes the piloting prototype, the main features pertaining to the location engine and to the water purification engine, and the further steps in pilot deployments. The solar cells studies are left out of this paper due to lack of space.

¹ <https://www.leap-re.eu/ledsol/>

2 LEDSOL system design and water-purification initial results

The overall system is shown in Fig. 1. The water purification unit contains three disinfection UV/LED-based tubes (number has been optimized based on tests), each equipped with four LEDs (one with UV-A and three with UV-C radiation), a particle filter and an active carbon filter, for the water purification; the full flow debit is $\sim 2\text{l/min}$, but it can also be adjusted to half flow rate for better purification results (the tradeoff is between the speed for delivering clean water to users and the purification efficacy). The whole system is powered by a power bank fed by a solar cell. A mobile location engine is also a part of the system; so far, Android mass-market devices available on the African market have been used. The prototype illustrated in

Fig. 1 Main building blocks of LEDSOL solution for clean and sustainable water access and integrated package; the three main blocks are the smart UV-LED-based water purification, a solar panel for a solar-powered solution, and a standalone wireless positioning support (in here through a mass-market mobile device).

Fig. 1 has been tested with water collected from three lakes in Bucharest; a snapshot of results is shown in Table 1 in terms of the amount of coliform bacteria in a water sample; these coliform bacteria are a group of microorganisms commonly found in the environment, including in soil, vegetation, and the intestines of warm-blooded animals and they are used as indicators of water quality and potential contamination. Tests regarding Faecal Streptococi were also conducted and found in only two of the three lakes, when found, these Streptococi were reduced to 0 after our disinfection process. We notice that reducing the flow rate to half gives better results at higher temperatures (37°C), but it reduces the speed to the clean water access from user side; we also notice a decrease in the coliform levels between 10 and 600 times, showing high efficacy of the prototype.

	Lake 1		Lake 2		Lake 3	
	TCC at 22° C	TCC at 37° C	TCC at 22° C	TCC at 37° C	TCC at 22° C	TCC at 37° C
Unpurified	118	1200	10	600	48	122
Purified, Maximum Flow Rate (~ 2 l/min)	4	16	1	19	12	16
Purified, Half Flow Rate (~ 1 l/min)	8	12	10	1	5	8

Table 1 Examples of water purification results achieved with LEDSOL prototype with 3 disinfection tubes and water taken from three lakes in Bucharest. TCC= Total Coliform Count.

3 Examples of location data analysis based on measurements in Africa

The location data has been collected in two manners for further analytics: 1) based on the GNSSlogger app of Google available via Google play on all Android devices (recent versions are also supported on Android wearables such as Google Pixel watch), and 2) through an in-house MIMIR Android app developed in our team and available in open-access on GitHub².

Fig. 2 Illustration of tracks collected in three different countries in Africa.

The collection of GNSS data in Africa has been so far limited to GNSSLogger data and encountered various challenges such as phone models not supporting the logging of raw data from all four GNSS systems (GPS, Galileo, Glonass, Beidou), scarce amount of viable measurements due, for example, to user-logging errors, etc. Therefore, we have also developed an in-house proprietary Matlab constellation simulator, supporting all four GNSS systems and allowing us a flexible further analysis of various location-based metrics of interest. Fig. 2 illustrated three tracks collected via GNSSLogger in Algeria, Togo, and Tanzania, while Fig. 3 shows some illustrative location-related statistics obtained with our simulator, based on these

² <https://github.com/agrenier-gnss/mimir>

tracks and assuming an outdoor non-line-of-sight wireless channel; statistics are done over 1 h or satellite in-orbit propagation with a 2 minute step and over 900 Monte Carlo runs. Fig. 4 shows the analysis of ionospheric, tropospheric, and other (e.g., multipath) errors based on the measured pseudoranges in Algeria and Tanzania. Due to limited space, only a snapshot of results is shown here.

Fig. 3 Illustration of the distributions Geometric Dilution of Precision (GDOP, left plot) and Carrier-to-Noise-Ratios (C/N_0 , right plot) based on our simulator and corresponding to the user tracks from Fig. 2

Fig. 4 Illustration of GPS errors based on measurement data in Algeria (left) and Tanzania (right).

We can see that, in terms of GDOP, we get very promising results, with GDOP values mostly below 3 in NLOS scenarios, which typically map to few meters of errors, which would be enough for an LBS in tracking and monitoring the LEDSOL water disinfection units. In terms of C/N_0 , we are still mostly below the nominal 30 – 35 dB-Hz target desirable in high-performance receivers, though the predicted values from simulations (see Fig. 3) are more pessimistic than the results achieved from field measurements (see Fig. 4), showing that we can predict the worst-case bounds via simulations, but there is place for enhancements in real-field scenarios, for example through GNSS and sensor integration solutions. The next steps towards integrating an LBS into the portable LEDSOL water management units are illustrated in Fig. 5. Now that we have got a good understanding of the GNSS data quality collected from Africa through GNSSLogger (the only app currently available on the devices of our collaborators in Africa), our own in-house MIMIR app can be expanded with data monitoring and analysis features, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Next steps in integrating the location-enabled reports in Ledsol solution.

The Ledsol system for test at fixed positions (static scenarios) has already been delivered to the Algeria and Togo research teams and static tests have started. The dynamic system, to be integrated in a backpack, is planned to be delivered in April 2025 and the dynamic tests will include not only the water purification results, but also a new collection of GNSS data for further analytics. At longer term, future location-enabled water management solutions could include, for example, location-enabled reports of the water quality issues, location-based delivery of clean water to areas in need, as well as the mobile-backpack tracking and monitoring for water-use-related statistics.

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